

Revolutionizing Neurodegenerative Disease: The Role of Neural Implants

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ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative diseases are advancing conditions marked by loss of neurons and neural function, resulting in cognitive and motor difficulties. Present therapies offers symptomatic relief but do not stop the advancement of the disease. Currently, there are no treatment that can reverse these diseases. The latest developments in microfluidic chip technologies, such as in-vitro brain-on-chip and in-vivo-like chip models, provide groundbreaking platforms for investigating. Chips designed for managing neurodegenerative diseases are sophisticated instruments that replicate the brain's environment in laboratory settings. In-vitro chips mimic the brain's cellular microenvironment, allowing for thorough studies of neurodegeneration, neuroinflammation, and blood-brain barrier dynamics. In-vivo chips replicate physiological aspects like vascular flow and multicellular interactions, connecting animal models to human clinical outcomes. These chipbased systems offer promising advancements for personalized medicine and creation of effective treatments for neurodegenerative diseases. Through targeted electrical stimulation and biomodulation, neural implants are transforming the treatment of neurodegenerative diseases by modulating neural activity and fostering functional recovery. These technologies offer the potential to convert neurorehabilitation into a tailored, dynamic process that tackles the progressive neural dysfunction typical of neurodegenerative diseases. Challenges persist in enhancing the biocompatibility of implants, reducing inflammatory reactions, and guaranteeing their long-term effectiveness and safety.

Keywords: Neurodegenerative Disease, Microchip, In-vivo Chips, In-vitro Chips, Neural implants.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) predicts that within the next 20 years, neurological illnesses will rank as the second most common cause of death worldwide. Biomedical scientists are motivated to study neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), Huntington disease (HD) and Multiple sclerosis(ML). Because of their rising prevalence in the aging population^[1]. A neurodegenerative disease is one that results from the death of neurons, which causes the brain tissue to lose its structural and functional characteristics^[2]. The goals of current ND medication therapy include calcium channel blocking, NMDA receptor antagonistic effects, neuroprotection, adjusting neurotransmitter levels, or using antibiotics, enzymes, and MAO inhibitors to treat ND symptoms^[3]. In AD,

memantine, an NMDA receptor antagonist, and cholinesterase inhibitors (donepezil, rivastigmine, and galantamine) enhance cognition and day-to-day functioning but do not stop neurodegeneration^[4]. The cornerstone of treatment consists of medications that prevent acetylcholine from being broken down in synapses. Galantamine, donepezil, and rivastigmine are safe medications, although they can cause cholinergic adverse effects include nausea, anorexia, diarrhea, vomiting, and weight loss. Slow drug titration can reduce these side effects, which are frequently self-limited. Although acetylcholinesterase inhibitors seem to work, the extent of their benefits might be higher in clinical trials than in real-world situations^[5]. Despite their limited therapeutic benefits, riluzole and edaravone for ALS somewhat increase survival or halt functional loss^[6]. Dopaminergic treatments like levodopa and dopamine agonists continue to be the mainstay of treatment for

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Parkinson's disease (PD), but deep brain stimulation (DBS) relieves more severe motor symptoms but does not stop the illness's development [4].

Although there are numerous approved treatments for neurodegenerative diseases (NDs) at the moment, the most of them merely aid in the treatment of the symptoms that are linked to the condition. Due to many obstacles related to NDs therapies, including the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and numerous unintended side effects of existing medications, the available medicines have not been able to control the progression of NDs, resulting in a reduced survival rate [7]. New therapeutic approaches must be created to address neurodegenerative illnesses in order to overcome the shortcomings of the available treatments. Many sophisticated compounds cannot be fully developed due to the absence of appropriate carriers for targeted medications [1]. On the surface, it would appear that innovation should concentrate on disease progression and prevention. However, it is also necessary to significantly enhance the management of acquired symptoms while preventing negative consequences [8].

Pathophysiology of neurodegenerative disease:

A broad category of incurable neurological conditions that affect people from early childhood to old age and have significant socioeconomic repercussions are known as neurodegenerative diseases (NDs). By 2050, it is anticipated that 150 million people worldwide will be afflicted by these illnesses, which include Huntington's disease (HD), Parkinson's disease (PD), Alzheimer's disease (AD), multiple sclerosis (MS), amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), and corticobasal syndrome (CBS), with an estimated 10 trillion dollars in economic impact [10].

Proteins are the basis for the molecular classification of neurodegenerative diseases. This highlights how pathogenesis involves protein-processing mechanisms. TAR-DNA-binding protein 43 kDa, tau, a-synuclein, prion protein, amyloid-b, and fused-in sarcoma protein are the most common proteins implicated in the pathophysiology of neurodegenerative disorders. Proteins encoded by genes linked to trinucleotide repeat diseases, neuroserpin, ferritin, and familial cerebral

amyloidoses are among the other proteins that are mostly linked to hereditary disorders [11].

The deposition of proteins with changed physicochemical characteristics, also referred to as misfolded proteins, is a significant characteristic. According to the theory of conformational disorders, a physiologic protein's structural shape might change, leading to a change in function or perhaps harmful intracellular or extracellular build-up [12].

Genes and proteins involved in neurodegenerative disease [11]:

1. Chromosome 17q21 encodes the sole gene for the microtubule-associated protein tau (MAPT).
2. The cleavage of Ab occurs from a big transmembrane precursor protein called amyloid precursor protein, or APP. The APP gene has been located in chromosome 21q21.3's centromeric region.
3. A single gene on chromosome 4 (SNCA) encodes alpha-synuclein.
4. The 253-amino acid protein known as prion protein (PrP) is encoded by the PrP gene; it is found on chromosome 20.
5. The highly conserved nuclear protein known as transactive response (TAR) DNA-binding protein43 (TDP-43) is encoded by the TARDBP gene on chromosome 16.
6. FET proteins, which include TATA-binding protein-associated Factor 15 (TAF15), Ewing sarcoma RNA-binding protein 1 (EWSR1), and fused-in sarcoma (FUS). The most studied is FUS, a protein with 526 amino acids that is encoded by a chromosome 16 gene.
7. Additional proteins are primarily linked to genetic diseases. These comprise, for instance, proteins expressed by genes associated with ferritin-related neurodegenerative illnesses,

neuroserpin, neurologic trinucleotide repeat disorders, and familial cerebral amyloidosis

Common mechanisms implicated in neurodegeneration:

Protein Aggregation^[10]:

A hallmark of NDs is protein aggregation, which is defined by the dispersion and dissemination of proteins such as Tau, α -synuclein (α -Syn), and amyloid β (A β) throughout the brain. Protein aggregates, which frequently involve several proteins, behave differently in various neurodegenerative diseases. Aggregation is thought to be the main source of NDs and is often facilitated by oligomerization and misfolding.

Amyloid and tau protein^[13]:

Aggregates are typically formed when misfolded proteins associate abnormally. Large protein aggregates precipitate out of solution under physiological conditions, although small aggregates can stay soluble. Amyloid fibrils and amorphous aggregates are the two main categories of aggregates that may be distinguished from a morphological perspective. The core portion of amyloid fibrils, which resemble thread-like protein aggregates, is made up of repeating arrays of sheets arranged perpendicular to the fibril axis. This structure is called a "cross" because it exhibits two sets of distinctive X-ray diffraction patterns. AD patients' brains are distinguished by two characteristics: (1) development of extracellular amyloid plaques by the cell surface receptor that is processed by alpha secretase and the proteolytic product of the amyloid precursor protein (APP), which is beta-amyloid cleavage enzyme, BACE1; (2) Hyperphosphorylated versions of the neuronal microtubule-associated protein tau create neurofibrillary tangles. In a healthy brain, alpha-secretase breaks down APP in a non-amyloidogenic manner, producing a secreted fragment and a C-terminal portion that gamma-secretase cleaves into smaller peptides that the cell may safely eliminate. In the amyloidogenic process, alpha-secretase cleaves APP rather than betasecretase and gamma-secretase then produces AB-peptide. There is a lot of interest in the function of metals in AD because of the evidence that metal ions can cause APP processing to shift towards the amyloid pathway and the high levels of trace metals in amyloid plaques. Alpha-secretase activity is influenced by Zn²⁺ and Fe^{2+/3+}, whereas

Cu²⁺ appears to have an impact. Similar to other neurodegenerative illnesses, AD also exhibits a highly localized loss of neuronal function in particular areas. Recent research has demonstrated a connection between A levels and glucose metabolism in AD, linking localized A deposition to local brain metabolism and neuronal activity.

Alpha-Synuclein:

The 140 amino acid presynaptic neuronal protein alpha-synuclein is present in a number of neurological disorders collectively referred to as synucleinopathies, the most well-known of which being Parkinson's Disease (PD) ^[11]. Before clinical symptoms appear, α -Syn aggregates accumulate, and their oligomers (α -SynO) can cause endoplasmic reticulum stress, destabilize proteins, damage synapses, induce apoptosis, and interfere with mitochondrial and nuclear function. Both recombinant and brain-derived α -Syn oligomers from multiple system atrophy (MSA) have the ability to cause certain pathogenic alterations in mice brains. Additionally, dementia with lewy bodies (DLB) and PD have been linked to α -Syn aggregates in astrocytes, which impair lysosomal autophagy and degradation and cause mitochondrial dysfunction in these cells ^[10].

Tau [14]:

Though it is expressed at extremely low levels in central nervous system (CNS) astrocytes and oligodendrocytes, tau is mostly found in the axons of central (CNS) and peripheral nervous system (PNS) neurons. It serves several vital roles in the assembly of microtubules (MTs) and is a typical part of the neuronal cytoskeleton. It can be phosphorylated on at least 79 of the putative phosphateacceptor Ser/Thr residues found on the longest tau isoform, which controls its function [66]. In a healthy brain, the balance between tau phosphorylation and dephosphorylation affects cytoskeleton stability and, in turn, axonal shape. The primary tau kinase in the brain, glycogen synthase kinase-3 (GSK3), and cyclin dependent kinase (Cdk5), a kinase involved in laminin activation and proper neurogenesis, have been primarily identified as responsible for the phosphorylative regulation of tau. GSK3 in particular shows markedly increased and selective tau

phosphorylation activity even after heat shock, which is sufficient to inhibit the remaining potential tau kinases- extracellular signal regulated kinase (ERK1/2), jun-N-terminal kinase (JNK) and cyclin dependent kinase (cdk5), indicating a key function for this kinase in the establishment of neurofibrillary tangles (NFT).

Prion protein [15]:

Endogenous cellular prion protein (PrPC) can be corrupted and changed into scrapie prion protein (PrPSc) by a little amount of PrPSc that is introduced to the host cell. During this transition, the protein's secondary structure clearly changes: the secondary structure of PrPC is dominated by α -helices, whereas that of PrPSc is dominated by β -sheets. A uncommon and crucial event that determines the pathophysiology of prion illnesses is the spontaneous α -to- β change in the prion protein's structure. This structural alteration is linked to pathological amyloid formation and aggregation through templating mechanisms in addition to loss of function. Amyloid assembly may not always be initiated by exogenous PrPSc. Prion illnesses with a hereditary or spontaneous origin can result from mutations that alter the structure of the endogenous prion protein, which can encourage the development of amyloid. In either case, the heterodimer forms fibrils upon the subsequent addition of PrPC, and these fibrils elongate to cause amyloid assembly. Depending on its structural stability, the expanding fibril may shatter and release fresh templates, which disperse and sustain the prion protein misfolding and aggregation chain reaction in various brain regions. PrPSc begins to build up in the impacted cells' late endocytic vesicles and lysosomes. PrPSc builds up inside cells, causing neurons to vacuolate and reactive astrocytes to proliferate, ultimately leading to neuronal death. PrPSc starts to build up extracellularly at this stage. The hallmark of prion illnesses, spongiform brain degeneration, increasing neural network instability, and increased neuronal death are caused by the polymerization of PrPSc to produce amyloid plaques.

Oxidative stress:

When reactive oxidative stress (ROS) are produced in excess of what antioxidant protection mechanisms can remove or when those systems are harmed,

problems arise. The pathophysiology of neuronal damage and acute and chronic CNS injury are both influenced by oxidative stress, which is the imbalance between the creation of ROS by cells and the cells' incapacity to protect against their consequences. In addition to damaging proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, oxidative stress may also open the mitochondrial permeability transition pore, which can increase energy failure, boost the generation of ROS, and release pro-apoptotic substances like cytochrome C into the cytoplasm³². Neuronal cell death occurs in neurodegenerative illnesses due to the production of excessive amounts of ROS and the downregulation of antioxidant mechanisms. Elevated oxygen levels cause Ca^{2+} homeostasis to be disturbed, which induces neurological deficits that show up as neuronal death. Through the deregulation of some equally important ion transport systems, such as ion channels (Ca^{2+} , K^{+} channels), ion pumps (Ca^{2+} pump, $\text{Na}^{+}/\text{K}^{+}$ ATPase), ion exchangers, and cotransporters ($\text{Na}^{+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger, $\text{K}^{+}/\text{Cl}^{-}$ cotransporter), which are essential for neurotransmission and synaptic function, oxidative stress is also thought to mediate subsequent perturbation of Ca^{2+} homeostasis via pathways other than ionotropic glutamate receptor stimulation. Since altered Ca^{2+} homeostasis is a crucial component of synaptic transmission, it is thought to play a key role in the development of AD pathogenesis. The precise chain of events is thought to be triggered by elevated oxygen radical levels, which disrupt Ca^{2+} homeostasis and tau phosphorylation, a process that is also thought to be induced. Studies performed on cultured cortical neurons and SH-SY-5Y neuroblastoma cell lines, however, provide evidence for a different sequence of events for mediated neurotoxicity, in which Ca^{2+} influx represents the initial step that precedes presentation of an oxidatively stressed environment and tau phosphorylation. Whatever the initiating event, both oxidative stress and alteration of Ca^{2+} homeostasis are known to culminate in neurological lesions in the AD brain that either manifest as neuronal loss due to apoptosis or necrosis, or synaptic loss [16].

Oxidative stress-induced apoptosis has been well-studied and is known to involve one of several different pathways, such as cytochrome C release and mitochondrial dysfunction, non-specific activation of caspase and calpain, lipid peroxidation, DNA

damage, and protein oxidation. Some of these pathways are also replicated in necrosis and in processes that result in a loss of Ca^{+2} homeostasis [14].

Mitochondrial Dysfunction:

Nuclear DNA encodes the remaining structural polypeptides and assembly factors, while mitochondria's own DNA (mtDNA) encodes 13 of the 92 polypeptides of the OXPHOS system. Tissues with high energy requirements, like the heart, skeletal muscle, and central nervous system, are known to be affected by mutations in either mtDNA or nuclear DNA that cause OXPHOS failure. It is believed that mitochondria cause aging by accumulating mtDNA mutations and producing a net amount of reactive oxygen species (ROS), thus mitochondrial dysfunction results in neuronal cell death. Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease are age-related neurodegenerative disorders that also include mitochondrial respiratory chain-deficient cells, mitochondrial abnormalities, and mitochondrial DNA alterations [17].

Due to their large calcium ion storage capacity, neuronal mitochondria can shield neurons from brief increases in intracellular calcium concentrations that occur during neuronal hyperactivity. Endothelial cells, astrocytes, and macrophages generate extra nitric oxide (NO) in inflammatory or ion-rich environments, which may result in oxidative stress. Nitric oxide (NO) is thought to be the chemical species responsible for tissue malfunction in neurological disorders, aging, and inflammation. Thus, by altering cellular calcium homeostasis, increasing the production of free radicals, or releasing apoptogenic proteins, mitochondrial malfunction can cause cell death [18].

Lysosomal Dysfunction:

Membrane-bound organelles called lysosomes have an acid lumen that is home to a variety of hydrolases that break down certain substrates. In addition to lysosomal storage disorder (LSDs), lysosomal dysfunction has been linked to neuropathology in the most prevalent types of neurodegenerative illnesses, including Parkinson's, Huntington's, and Alzheimer's. LSDs trigger a number of lysosomal-dependent pathogenic cascades, including oxidative stress,

inflammation, altered lipid trafficking, endoplasmic reticulum stress, autoimmune reactions, decreased autophagic flux, and altered calcium homeostasis. The pathophysiology of LSDs is significantly influenced by autophagy dysfunction [18]. When autophagy fails in neurons, toxic substrates, aggregate-prone proteins, and damaged organelles accumulate subsequent to one another. Since toxic storage is a key factor in post-mitotic cell death, including in neurons, it sets off neurodegenerative processes. In fact, healthy autophagic pathways are essential for preserving regular neuronal function [22], and any reduction in their capacity to degrade neuronal material plays a role in the pathophysiology of both age-related neurodegenerative diseases and LSDs [19].

Neurotropic factors:

According to certain theories, the neurotrophic factor family helps safeguard some neuronal populations by inhibiting the production of "suicide genes," which trigger apoptotic processes when they are activated [14, 236, 359]. According to this theory, transcriptional processes may cause apoptotic mechanisms to be triggered when neurotrophic factor expression levels drop below what is needed to prevent the activation of "suicide genes." If mature neurons still rely on neurotrophic factors for survival and function, then the loss of transcriptional suppression of the "suicide program" brought on by a decrease in the expression of neurotrophic factors may be the cause of the neuronal loss seen in neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease or the neuronal atrophy seen in normal aging [20]. Cell shrinkage, chromatin condensation, nuclear fragmentation, plasma membrane blebbing, and the development of membrane-bound apoptotic bodies are among the morphological characteristics of apoptosis, a kind of controlled cell death (RCD). Extracellular death ligands (TNF- α , FASL, TRAIL, etc.) can bind to death receptors to initiate the apoptotic pathway (extrinsic pathway); on the other hand, cellular injury (DNA damage, metabolic stress, ROS) may cause mitochondrial membrane depolarization, which may start the intrinsic pathway [21, 22]. Necrosis represents an uncontrolled, passive form of cell death usually induced by severe cellular stress or injury, such as oxidative damage, excitotoxicity, or energy failure.

Necrotic cells typically undergo rapid swelling, membrane rupture, and subsequent release of intracellular contents into the surrounding tissue, provoking a robust inflammatory response^[23,24].

Ageing :

The human brain changes in a number of ways as we age. With age, the human brain shrinks. The loss of neurons and myelinated axons is thought to be the cause of the aging brain's decreased weight and volume. One of the main characteristics of the aging brain is changes in the white

matter [25].

The loss of irreplaceable cells, which is most prominent in the brain, heart, and skeletal muscles, is a significant alteration that occurs with time. Neurons in the brain atrophy and die, while networks and connections between neurons change. The loss of neurons, especially in the hypothalamus's sensitive regions, is linked to mental and emotional abnormalities in the aged and may be a contributing factor to some physiological alterations like altered metabolism and circadian rhythm. Dopamine, norepinephrine, serotonin, tyrosine hydroxylase, and cholinesterase all decline with age, whereas monoamine oxidase activity rises. Increasing oxidative stress, deteriorating mitochondrial function, telomere erosion, poor DNA repair, and reduced tissue regeneration are all linked to aging at the cellular level^[26].

Excitotoxicity^[16]:

The brain's primary excitatory system is made up of glutamatergic neurons, which are essential for numerous neurophysiological processes. Glutamate, which causes an excitatory response, is the main neurotransmitter in the brain's basic perception and cognition under normal circumstances. This reaction is produced after glutamate interacts with the receptors that make up cation channels. Excitotoxicity is the term for the process by which excessive glutamate receptor activation can cause neuronal malfunction and death. Certain neurodegenerative illnesses are characterized by an excess of glutamate and glutamatergic activity. Glutamate receptor overactivation disrupts calcium homeostasis inside cells and triggers the production of nitric oxide, free

radicals, and programmed cell death. Excitotoxicity is the term used to describe cell death brought on by excitatory amino acids' harmful effects. As the primary excitatory neurotransmitter in the mammalian central nervous system (CNS), glutamate causes neuronal excitotoxicity, which is the term used to describe the damage and death of neurons brought on by extended exposure to glutamate and the resulting excessive ion input. Because of the ensuing calcium overload, which is especially neurotoxic, enzymes that break down proteins, membranes, and nucleic acids are activated.

Drugs used in Parkinson's disease:

Although there are presently no disease-modifying medications for Parkinson's disease (PD), the available medicines can significantly reduce motor symptoms. They don't provide much clinical help for PD's non-motor symptoms. In order to lessen the impact of side effects, it is customary to postpone starting therapy until the patient's symptoms become problematic^[27].

Dopaminergic symptom relief treatment, encompass the following new subcategories and are used to describe striatum (ST) medicines that either imitate, restore, or replace the neurotransmitter dopamine^[28]:

DA agonist

Reformulation of levodopa(LD)

Non-dopaminergic symptom relief therapies, refers to ST medications that target neurotransmitter systems other than dopamine and Incorporate:

Adrenergic Cholinergic

NMDA.

Serotonergic non-DA and ST

Anti-inflammatory, refers to substances that aim to lessen inflammatory processes.

Antioxidants, are substances whose main goal is to lessen oxidative stress

Levodopa:

Levodopa-based preparations, which are intended to replenish the dopamine in the depleted striatum, are

the cornerstone of modern PD therapy. Levodopa, a dopamine precursor, can be used as a treatment since it can penetrate the blood-brain barrier. DOPA decarboxylase transforms it into the neurotransmitter dopamine following absorption and passage across the blood-brain barrier [27].

Pharmacological actions: Parkinsonian individuals experience a noticeable improvement in their symptoms. Rigidity and hypokinesia go away first, followed by tremor. Gradually, secondary symptoms related to posture, walking, handwriting, speech, facial expression, mood, self-care, and life interest become normal. Levodopa's behavioral effects have been characterized as general alerting response. Side effects: Treatment-related symptoms include nausea and vomiting, cardiac arrhythmia, postural hypotension, and taste changes. After prolongation of therapy; dyskinesias, or abnormal movements, and behavioral consequences, such as anxiety, mania, sadness, and mental disorientation, can occur after therapy has been ongoing [29].

Amantadine :

Demonstrating improvements in Parkinson's disease. not as effective as levodopa. It's unclear what the mechanism of action is. It has an antagonistic effect on the NMDA type of glutamate receptor, which is how the striatal dopaminergic system works, and it stimulates the brain's presynaptic production and release of dopamine [29].

Pharmacological actions: Amantadine is now used mostly for Parkinson disease. Clinical trials have shown that amantadine decreases bradykinesia, rigidity, and tremor symptoms. There is a combined synergistic effect with added levodopa, which is converted to dopamine by striatal enzymes in the CNS. There can be a transient benefit to the drug, so short-term therapy for patients with the mild disease is best [30].

Side effects include insomnia, agitation, disorientation, nightmares, anticholinergic effects, and hallucinations [29].

Dopaminergic agonist (apomorphine, ropinirole, pramipexole) [31] :

In early PD, ropinirole and pramipexole are used as monotherapy; in late PD, they are used as a complement to levodopa-carbidopa. Pharmacological actions: Dopamine agonists postpone levodopa-related side effects such as dyskinesias and motor fluctuations when they are used early in Parkinson's disease treatment. Dyskinesias are less common with ropinirole than with levodopa. Side effects include postural changes, hallucinations, nausea, and dizziness. behavioral adverse effects such as excessive sexual activity, impulsive buying, gaming. Being lipophilic and water soluble, apomorphine is a nonergoline dopamine agonist that may be administered intravenously, subcutaneously, sublingually or transdermally. Oropharyngeal side effects are among them.

Selegiline:

Selegiline is an irreversible, selective monoamine oxidase (MAO-B) inhibitor. In early instances, it has moderate antiparkinsonism effect. Selegiline blocks the MAO enzyme, which breaks down dopamine in the brain. As a result, selegiline increases dopamine availability by preventing its breakdown [29].

Pharmacological actions: By encouraging the synthesis of neurotrophins such as brain-derived neurotrophic factor, nerve growth factor, and glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor, selegiline may have neuroprotective effects and perhaps decrease the course of Parkinson disease [32].

Side effects: Postural hypotension, nausea, disorientation and sleeplessness are some of the side symptoms [29].

Drugs used for Alzheimer's disease:

The only FDA-approved drugs for AD are the N-methyl D-aspartate (NMDA) antagonist memantine, galantamine, rivastigmine, and donepezil, which are acetylcholinesterase inhibitors (AChEIs) [33].

AChEI:

By blocking the acetylcholinesterase enzyme in the synaptic cleft, AChEIs aim to lessen the breakdown of acetylcholine levels in the brains of AD patients. While rivastigmine is a "pseudoirreversible" inhibitor of both acetylcholinesterase and

butyrylcholinesterase, donepezil and galantamine exclusively and reversibly inhibit acetylcholinesterase^[33].

Adverse effects include bradycardia, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, syncope risk, and rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder^[33].

Memantine:

Glutamatergic transmission is impacted by memantine, a noncompetitive low-affinity NMDA receptor open-channel blocker. AChEIs and memantine can be used together since their methods of action are complimentary^[33].

Memantine works by inhibiting voltage-gated cation channels called NMDA receptors, which stops them from being overstimulated and lowers the amount of calcium that enters cells.

Glutamate transporters found in brain glial cells aid in preserving the sodium (Na⁺) and potassium (K⁺) ion transmembrane gradient. By causing tau protein hyperphosphorylation and excitotoxicity-induced neuronal cell death, calcium plays a crucial part in the pathophysiology of dementia^[34].

Pharmacological actions: Memantine can slow the long-term progression of AD through neuroprotective actions is consistent with the ability of memantine to inhibit NMDAR responses. However, memantine also demonstrates therapeutic benefits, such as increases in cognitive ability, after as little as two weeks of therapy^[35].

Side effects: Dizziness, headaches, constipation, disorientation, urinary tract infections, somnolence, and agitation are common adverse effects linked to the medication treatment^[34].

Aducanumab:

In a dose-dependent way, Aducanumab (human IgE antibody) eliminates both soluble and insoluble A β from the human brain and stops it from aggregating^[34].

Pharmacological action: By instructing the body's immune system to eliminate the A β plaques, aducanumab reduces A β in the brain^[36].

Side effects: ARIA, headache, vision changes, dizziness, confusion, and nausea, Swelling of the lips, mouth, tongue, face, and hives^[34].

Lecanemab:

Lecanemab reverses the development of AD and has a greater selectivity for bigger soluble beta amyloid protofibrils^[34].

Pharmacological actions: slowing the progression of neuronal damage and cognitive deterioration in Alzheimer's patients. suppression of neuroinflammation and activation of the plasma contact system caused by A β protofibrils^[37,38].

The following are side effects: cerebral edemas (ARIAs), Microhemorrhages or vasogenic edemas, a disease in which blood leaks into parenchymal tissues, can result from these adverse effects.

Patients may experience headaches, dizziness, disorientation, seizures, or even death^[24].

Drugs used for Huntington disease:

Tetrabenazine:

Tetrabenazine (TBZ) was the first medication authorized to treat chorea linked to Huntington's disease^[18]. At low dosages, it primarily functions as a reversible high affinity inhibitor of monoamine absorption into presynaptic neurons' granular vesicles and secondary depletion; at high concentrations, it functions as a weak D2 postsynaptic receptor blocker^[39].

Pharmacological actions: Presynaptic dopamine and other monoamines are reduced, which results in less hyperkinetic movements^[40].

Adverse effects include akathisia, sadness, sleeplessness, sleepiness, parkinsonism, and anxiety

[18].

Deutetrabenazine:

DBZ is an isotopic isomer of TBZ that has a longer half-life but depletes central monoamines by reversibly inhibiting vesicular monoamine transporter (VMAT2)^[18].

Pharmacological actions: Enhanced motor control is a result of monoamine neurotransmission modulation. Deutetrabenazine may have additional effects on dopaminergic and serotonergic receptors^[41].

Side effects include agitation, sadness, sleepiness, sleeplessness, parkinsonism, and depression and suicidality^[18].

Drugs used in Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis:

(1,6-(Trifluoromethoxy)-2-Benzothiazolamine, or riluzole:

This medication reduces excitotoxicity in a number of ways. Riluzole is believed to have some neuroprotective properties. This is because its anti-glutamatergic drug functions as a particular sodium channel blocker on presynaptic neurons, preventing the presynaptic release of the neurotransmitter glutamate. Furthermore, it increases GABA receptors and decreases gammaaminobutyric acid (GABA) reuptake. According to recent research, riluzole has a different mechanism of action (MOA). It suppresses excitotoxicity by blocking the catalytic activity of the protein kinase, casein kinase (CK1 δ), preventing the cytoplasmic compartmentalization of TDP43 (transactive response DNA binding protein of 43 k^[39].

Pharmacological actions: By lowering glutamate-mediated excitotoxicity by sodium channel blockage and improving glutamate clearance, riluzole slightly increases survival. Rather than a noticeable increase in cognition or behavior, its primary known effect is the halting of motor

degeneration^[42,43,44].

Asthenia, lightheadedness, and gastrointestinal issues are side effects^[39].

Edaravone:

Edaravone is a free radical scavenger that works by removing lipid peroxy radicals and peroxy nitrate, therefore protecting motor neurons from oxidative stress and free radical damage. Additionally, edaravone's antioxidant qualities and capacity to lessen the buildup of mutant superoxide dismutase (SOD1) have proven its effectiveness^[39].

Pharmacological actions: Edaravone, primarily an antioxidant, exhibits neuroprotection by lowering oxidative stress and may indirectly improve cognition by maintaining the integrity of neurons^[45].

Contusion, disorientation, constipation, eczema, headache, bruises, irregular gait, and contact dermatitis are some of the adverse effects^[39].

WHAT IS CHIP ?

A microchip, also known as a chip, computer chip, or integrated circuit (IC), is a system of integrated circuitry made at the microscopic level from semiconductor materials like silicon or, to a lesser extent, germanium. It consists of a collection of electrical circuits on a tiny, flat piece of silicon. Layers of electronic components, including resistors and transistors, are etched into the material, along with complex connections that bind the parts together and allow electric impulses

to flow^[46,47].

Microfluidic culture systems known as “in vitro chips,” or “organ-on-a-chip devices,” mimic the physiological conditions of human organs outside of the body. These chips provide a platform for simulating dynamic mechanical stimuli like shear stress and cyclic strain, which are essential to replicating in vivo conditions like intestinal peristalsis. They enable long-term cell culture and monitoring, supporting complex biological functions like epithelial barrier formation and immune cell interactions. The design flexibility and integration of sensors facilitate high-throughput analysis and personalized medicine applications. They use living human cells cultured in microchannels on a chip to mimic organ function and drug response^[48,49].

In-vivo measurements are crucial because they are carried out directly on living tissue using either internal or external equipment. Many additional uses have resulted from the devices' and the system's (sensor, electronics, power, and communication) downsizing, making them suitable for use as internal devices^[50].

Table 1: Types of in- vitro Chips

Types of intro chips	Description	Application	References
Organ-on-a-Chip (OoC)	Microengineered systems that replicate the structure and function of human organs using living cells in microfluidic platforms.	Drug discovery, disease modeling, toxicology, personalized medicine.	51,52
Brain-on-a-Chip	Devices that simulate brain tissue and blood-brain barrier using 2D/3D cultures, allowing advanced neurological research.	Disease modeling (Alzheimer's, parkinsonism), neurotoxicity, drug permeability studies.	51
Liver-on-a-Chip	Microfluidic chips designed to model liver tissue, including lobules and bile ducts with convectivediffusive blood flow.	Drug metabolism, toxicity testing, liver disease research.	53
Kidney-on-a-Chip	Chips that recreate nephron functions, including filtration and tubular secretion using multi-layer microfluidics.	Nephrotoxicity studies, kidney disease modeling, drug safety assessment.	53
Multi-Organ-on-aChip	Integration of two or more organ models through microfluidic channels to simulate systemic interactions.	Whole-body pharmacology, multi-organ disease modeling, personalized drug responses.	54
Heart-on-a-Chip	Chips replicating contractile cardiac tissue and its electrical activity in controlled platforms.	Cardiotoxicity testing, drug screening, cardiovascular disease research.	55

Table 2: Types of in- vivo chips

Types of in vivo chips	Description	Application	References
Neural Implants (Brain Chips)	Implantable devices with electrode arrays placed in the brain to record/stimulate neurons	Brain-computer interfaces, treatment of neurological diseases (Parkinson's, epilepsy, paralysis)	56
Implantable Biosensors	Chips sensing biological/chemical signals in vivo; may be continuous or ondemand	Blood glucose monitoring, cardiac monitoring, metabolic tracking	56,57
Cardiac Pacemakers/Stimulators	Electronic devices implanted to regulate heart rhythm or stimulate nerves	Treatment of arrhythmias, heart failure, chronic pain	54
Subderma Interface Chips	Flat or cylindrical devices placed under skin layers that can interface with mobile systems.	Personal access systems, smart device control, data encryption.	58
Retinal/Cochlear Implants	Microelectronic chips implanted in the eye or ear to restore sensory function	Vision and hearing restoration	56,57

Neural implants as in- vivo chip:

An implant is a man-made device that is inserted into the body by surgery or injection. A neural implant is a device that is inserted into the body and communicates with neurons, which are electrical cells. Similar to Morse code, they shoot electrical impulses in certain patterns. By recording native brain activity, these implants enable researchers to see the communication patterns of healthy neural circuits. Additionally, neural implants have the ability to provide electrical pulses to neurons, overriding their natural firing patterns and compelling them to communicate in a new manner^[58].

Neural implants perform a wide range of roles in medicine. Cochlear implants, for instance, can assist some individuals who are hard of hearing regain their hearing, while other kinds of implants can aid with neuropathic pain, Parkinson's disease symptoms, and epileptic convulsions^[59]. By altering aberrant brain activity, deep brain stimulation (DBS) implants successfully cure neurological and psychiatric conditions such as Parkinson's disease, epilepsy, depression, and obsessive-compulsive disorder. Additionally, neural implants have the ability to improve cognitive function, manage pain, and deliver drugs to specific brain regions, increasing the specificity of treatment for illnesses of the central nervous system^[60,61,62].

Table 3: components of neural implants

Components of chip	Material used	Function	References
Electrodes	Platinum(Pt), Gold (Au), Iridium(Ir), Tungsten (W), Carbon Nanotubes, PEDOT:PSS (conductive polymer)	Electrical signal recording and stimulation	63,64,65
Substrate	Polyimide, Parylene C, Poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS), Silicone	Provide biocompatibility and flexibility to electrode	64,66
Semiconductor Chip	Silicon-based CMOS chips	Wireless communication, signalling amplification	67
Encapsulation Layer	Parylene C, Silicone, Epoxy, Polymers	Protect from corrosion and Biocompatible support	64
Connection Leads	Gold, Platinum, flexible polymer wiring	Electrical interconnection between ICs and electrodes	65,66
Implantation Shuttle	Silicon, Biodegradable polymers (PEG)	Temporary stiff insertion aid for flexible probes	64

Mechanism of action:

Insertion & immediate tissue damage: Insertion and immediate tissue damage: Blood vessels and brain tissue are cut when the electrode or probe is introduced. Cell death, hemorrhage, and the release of damage signals are all briefly triggered by this. Later immunological reactions are predicated on that original insult^[63,68].

Acute inflammation (hours → days): d-borne immune cells and microglia quickly arrive at the site, remove debris, and release cytokines. This acute inflammation alters the local chemical environment

(ions, neurotransmitters) and is a typical wound reaction^[69,70].

Chronic foreign-body response and encapsulation (days → months): Astrocytes and microglia create a glial "scar" or encapsulation around the implant as the tissue develops a chronic response over a period of weeks to months. This lowers signal quality and raises electrical resistance between the electrode and neurons. This foreign-body reaction frequently limits long-term performance^[63,69].

Detection of Neural Electrical Activity (Recording): Action potentials are electrical impulses that neurons use to communicate. Microelectrodes in neural

implants are capable of detecting these voltage variations. The implant records the electrical patterns produced by firing neurons and transforms them into digital signals. An external processor receives this recorded data after that^[72].

Distance to active neurons (signals rapidly decrease with distance): electrode impedance and surface area, and local tissue conductivity (modified by inflammation/encapsulation) all affect recording. Slower field potentials and spikes (rapid action potentials) can be observed if neurons are close together and in good health^[71].

Interpretation and Signal Processing: Neural signals are filtered, amplified, and decoded once they are recorded. The device can read movement intention, sensory data, or irregular brain rhythms thanks to sophisticated algorithms that spot patterns in neuronal firing. This stage is particularly crucial for neuroprosthetics and brain-computer interfaces^[73].

Electrical Stimulation of Neural Circuits: A lot of neural implants stimulate neural tissue in addition to recording. Neural activity can be modulated by electrical pulses given through the electrodes. For instance: Parkinson's disease-related aberrant brain rhythms are lessened by stimulation in DBS. Stimulation in sensory implants (such as cochlear or visual implants) imitates natural sensory input^[74].

Action potentials are produced by direct depolarization of axons or cell bodies close to the electrode, activation or blockage of neural elements (axonal activation is frequently simpler than soma activation), recruitment of local inhibitory/excitatory circuits, and alterations in neurotransmitter release. This stimulation restores or enhances function by altering the way neurons activate^[75,76].

Electrochemical interface and safety limits with the modulation of neural circuits and plasticity: Electrochemistry at the interface and electrode materials affect stimulation and recording. Device parameters must adhere to material limits because exceeding safe charge density results in electrochemical reactions, tissue damage, and electrode corrosion^[77,78]. Over time, stimulation can rearrange brain networks, a phenomenon known as neuroplasticity. Continuous modulation may reduce

malfunctioning neural networks and boost beneficial ones. Long-term gains in movement, memory, behavior, or sensory perception are facilitated by this step^[79].

Output Transmission and Functional Response: Ultimately, the processed or modulated neural signals produce quantifiable results, such as a robotic arm moving through BCI output, tremors decreasing through DBS, improved sensory perception through stimulation, and stabilization of cognitive or emotional circuits. Neural activity is linked to practical behavioral or clinical improvements in this step^[80].

Neuralink:

The implant is known as the N1 Implant or "the Link." Neuralink chip uses thin, flexible threads equipped with 1,024 electrodes that record the activity of neurons, the nerve cells that send messages all over the body to drive nearly all human functions. The coin-sized device is powered by an advanced custom chip within the implant that processes these signals and transmits them to a digital device through a standard Bluetooth connection- a novel step in brain-computer-interface (BCI) development. Surgical robots meticulously weave these threads into the cerebral cortex, which is responsible for the brain's higher-level processes like learning and emotion, to ensure precise placement of the electrodes^[67]. The electrical chemical signals in our nervous system spark as neurons communicate with one another across gaps between nerve cells known as synapses. This brain activity is captured by electrodes, or sensors that detect voltages, measuring the change in "spikes" of when these voltages fire (or potentially fire)^[81].

Applications:

1. By modifying neuronal circuits by electrical stimulation akin to deep brain stimulation (DBS), Neuralink may help manage conditions like Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, or ALS^[82,83].
2. By capturing neural impulses from the motor cortex and sending them to external devices or muscles, Neuralink seeks to restore movement in people with spinal cord injuries^[84,85].

3. By directly activating the relevant brain cortex and avoiding damaged sensory nerves, Neuralink may aid in the restoration of sensory inputs like sight and hearing^[83,86].
4. Through focused neuromodulation, Neuralink may help cure depression, anxiety, or obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) by controlling aberrant brain activity^[87,88].

Blackrock:

The Utah Array is a high-channel count microelectrode array. The Utah Array has a few key performance features: 100 active electrode channels per implant; can be customized up to 1,024 channels, typical configurations include four to six devices (400-600 electrodes), ability to reliably pick up signals from both individual neurons and a summation of high-resolution signals, variety of connector types for acute or chronic recording, electrode site metal options: iridium oxide or platinum, standard electrode lengths: 0.5-1.5 mm (research) or 1.0-1.5 mm (clinical). This bundle of microelectrodes, also known as the NeuroPort Array, remains the only FDA-cleared highchannel microelectrode platform that can record signals from individual neurons and that is used in BCI applications for movement disorders. ^[89].

Applications:

1. The Utah Array uses neural impulses to enable typing and communication for people with ALS or total paralysis^[90].
2. Patients with tetraplegia can operate prosthetics, computer cursors, and robotic arms using just neural signals thanks to the Blackrock implant^[91].
3. Neural population coding, decision-making, movement planning, and sensory processing are all extensively studied using the Utah Array^[92].

Infinity dbs :

DBS systems include implanted devices, similar to pacemakers, that deliver mild electrical pulses through thin wires, called leads. Parkinson's disease is caused by a loss of dopamine-producing cells in the brain: Dopamine has a key role in movement function.

As dopamine deficiencies grow, medications can become less effective and create increased side effects. DBS therapy is like an electrical version of dopamine, stabilizing circuits of the brain to reduce involuntary movements. DBS therapy from Abbott has been shown to help people with Parkinson's disease reduce medication. With the Infinity™ DBS System's directional lead technology, these pulses are sent directly to targeted areas of the brain for focused stimulation. The stimulator device sends electrical pulses through the lead to regulate signals in the brain. The stimulation level is prescribed by your physician—either in person or remotely (only with the Abbott system)—to control involuntary movements, and can be adjusted through your patient controller ^[93].

Applications:

1. By activating the subthalamic nucleus (STN) or globus pallidus internus (GPI), Infinity DBS is frequently used to treat motor symptoms such tremor, stiffness, and bradykinesia^[94].
2. In certain facilities, Infinity DBS stimulates the sensory thalamus to treat refractory neuropathic pain^[95].

Sensors used in chips for management of neurodegenerative disease

The development of implanted sensors has been driven by the demand for more precise physiological recordings specific to the circumstances in the vicinity of a clinically relevant physiological event. Ideally, these can even provide a real-time closed-loop intervention or therapy^[96]. Today, implantable sensors can provide accurate *in vivo* measurements of biophysical and bioelectrical parameters, as well as specific biomarkers such as ions (e.g., Na⁺, K⁺, and Ca²⁺), neurotransmitters (e.g., serotonin, epinephrine, norepinephrine, serotonin, and dopamine), hormones (e.g., melatonin and cortisol), and volatile organic compounds (e.g., acetone, isopropyl alcohol, and isoprene) ^[97].

Implantable sensors are devices that are placed in the body to measure various biological parameters or biomarkers^[98].

Table 4: Sensors used in in-vivo chips

Type of sensor	Working	Uses	References
Neurochemical Sensors	Electrochemical probes detect neurotransmitters (e.g., dopamine, glutamate) via redox reactions	Monitoring neurotransmitter dynamics in brain disorders (e.g., Parkinson's, Alzheimer's)	99,100
Microelectrode Arrays (MEAs)	Arrays of microelectrodes record electrical activity from neurons	Tracking neural electrophysiology, brain-computer interfaces, neurodegenerative disease progression	63,101
Electrocorticography (ECoG) Arrays	Surface electrodes measure integrated field potentials of neurons over cortex	Diagnosis and monitoring of epilepsy, Parkinson's, and other neurodegenerative disorders	101
Optical Neural Sensors	Fluorescence or bioluminescence sensors genetically encoded or implanted	Imaging neurotransmission and signaling in vivo for research on neurodegeneration	102

Future scope:

Growing brain-on-a-chip and organoid-on-a-chip platforms that replicate patient-specific neural circuits for precise disease modeling and drug screening. Bringing together microfluidics, stem cells, and biomaterials to develop physiologically relevant microenvironments that replicate characteristics of brain tissue and the blood-brain barrier.

Use of in vivo implantable chips with wireless and minimally invasive designs for adaptive neuromodulation therapies aimed at conditions such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and ALS. Broaden the use of these technologies for personalized medicine, enabling drug screening tailored to individual genetic and pathological profiles. Progress in biomaterials and engineering aimed at enhancing biocompatibility, sensor integration, and real-time tracking of disease development or treatment efficacy. Possibility of integrating chips with gene editing and stem cell therapies to create new regenerative treatments.

CONCLUSION

Current drug treatments for neurodegenerative diseases mainly manage symptoms but don't stop disease progression. In vitro brain-on-a-chip and organoid-on-chip models enable detailed mechanistic investigations, drug screening, and insights into

neurodegenerative pathology in Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and ALS, thereby accelerating preclinical innovation. Implantable chips, such as adaptive deep brain stimulators and advanced brain-computer interfaces, used in vivo can restore motor, cognitive, and communicative functions in patients suffering from neurodegeneration and paralysis, leading to significant quality of life enhancements. Currently, untreatable neurodegenerative disease have possibility of becoming treatable with invivo implants. Compared to drugs, these chips offer more precise and dynamic treatment options. Together, they complement traditional drugs, promising better outcomes by combining technological pathways with active brain interaction.

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